

Deer Antlers vs Cancer

EKATERINA ARTEAGA

Nature's Gift

- Deer antlers grow very fast – they regenerate completely
- Due to this rapid division of cells one might think that they will get cancer more often than other mammals, but the opposite happens
- Genetic changes allow to protect them from cancer

Similarities

- The rapidly dividing cells can be seen in osteosarcoma
- Interestingly, the cells found in antlers in terms of the genes they express look more like cancer cells of osteosarcoma than regular cells
- That led to a belief that there must be cancer regulating activity

Comparison

- C-FOS gene expressed by antler cells – problematic gene, tells the cells to divide more
- However, to counter balance those genes deer has a gene Tp53 seen in other animals that suppress cancer – checks for DNA damage
- They don't have extra copies of that genes but they have other genes to help to control cancer - proto-oncogenes

Deer Antler Velvet (DAV) vs Cancer Cells (GB)

- Deer Antler Velvet (DAV) – its extract proves to be beneficial to reduce proliferation in humans
- In the study they took GB cell lines and treated them with DAV from the tip of the antler to see how it would affect cancerous activity
- They assessed the cells' ability to proliferate, colony-formation capacity, scratch assay

RESULTS

- The results were:
- In GB cell lines it inhibited cancerous activity:
 - cell migration (scratch assay)
 - tumor clonogenic assay
 - proliferation - cells were arrested in the S and G2/M phases
 - could induce both early and late apoptosis
- In non-cancerous cell lines it had a non-toxic effect

Figure 2

Figure 3

Conclusions

Title and Content Layout with Chart

Project by science club
member:Khatia Devadze

MYSTERY OF ELEPHANTS

Project Overview

In this presentation, we discuss how elephants manage to have a very low risk of cancer despite their size

LIFETIME RISK OF CANCER	<5%	25%	33-50%	90%
CANCER MORTALITY RATE	<5%	50%	25%	n/a*
TP53 GENE	40	2	2	1

*Not Available /// SOURCE: Joshua Schiffman

Elephants breaking the rules of nature !

- A greater number of cells and cell divisions increases the chance of accumulating mutations resulting in malignant transformation
- If all mammalian cells are equally susceptible to oncogenic mutations, then cancer risk should increase with body size and species life span

cancer incidence across animals does not appear to increase as theoretically expected for larger body size and number of cells

elephants have at least 20 copies of Tp53, a gene known as the 'guardian of the genome'

TP53

Encodes protein p53

Endogenous Stress

DNA Damage

Exogenous Stress

TP53

p53

Angiogenesis

Recruitment

Oxidative Stress

Cell Cycle Arrest

Apoptosis

DNA Repair

The research

Design: A comprehensive survey of necropsy data was performed across 36 mammalian species. PBL analysis tested in vitro in the laboratory for DNA damage response (University of Utah between June 2014 and July 2015), genome analysis.

Objective : cellular response to DNA damage among elephants, healthy human controls, and cancer-prone patients with Li-Fraumeni syndrome (LFS).

Participants:

- elephants (n = 644)
- African and Asian elephants (n = 8)
 - patients with LFS (n = 10)
- age-matched human controls (n = 11)

Laboratory experiments:

peripheral blood lymphocytes

fibroblasts (confirmatory)

hek293 (confirmatory)

Exposures

a type of chemotherapy drug called an anthracycline.

TP53 Retrogene Transcription and Translation

Transfected HEK293 cells showed p53 retrogene 9 protein expression by immunoblotting that increased with DNA damage similar to p53 in human fibroblasts exposed to DNA damage

Results

Zoo Necropsies and Cancer Mortality

•
•

Among 644 annotated elephant deaths from the Elephant Encyclopedia database, the lifetime cancer incidence was 3.11%

Results

•
•

Results: Elephant Cell Response to DNA Damage

African elephant PBLs demonstrated apoptosis at significantly elevated rates compared with human PBLs after 18 hours when exposed to 2 Gy of ionizing radiation

33.20% VS 14.07%

A African elephant PBLs 5 h after 2 Gy ionizing radiation

B Human PBLs 5 h after 2 Gy ionizing radiation

Results: TP53 Retrogene Transcription and Translation

- the TP53 retrogenes may functionally increase elephant cell response to DNA damage by triggering p53-dependent apoptosis rather than increasing DNA repair.

- Apoptosis can prevent mutations from propagating to future cell generations through removal of mutated clones. The elephant cells appeared twice as sensitive to DNA damage-induced apoptosis as human cells.

Conclusion

- Compared with other mammalian species, elephants appeared to have a lower-than-expected rate of cancer, potentially related to multiple copies of TP53
- Compared with human cells, elephant cells demonstrated increased apoptotic response following DNA damage.

Thank you!

Do you have any questions?

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Ketevan Vepkhvadze • 28/06/2024

Axolotl regeneration

For “science club”

ANATOMY OF THE AXOLOTL

Trauma

Wound healing

Blastema growth

AXOLOTL

LIMB REGENERATION

Re-development

Re-differentiation

tail
gills
heart
liver
lungs
spinal cord
telencephalon
tooth
eye lens
ovaries

The timeline of blasthema formation

1. 0-24 hpa

- mTOR Activation: The mTOR pathway is activated in response to amino acid release at the injury site.
- Protein Synthesis: Rapid translation of mRNAs necessary for cell proliferation and wound healing.
- ROS Production: Injury-induced ROS are managed for effective signaling in tissue repair.

2. 1-3 dpa

- Wound Epithelium Formation: Epithelial cells migrate to cover the wound.
- Cell Proliferation and Dedifferentiation: Cells near the wound site proliferate and dedifferentiate into a more primitive state.

3. 4-14 dpa

- Blastema Formation: A collection of dedifferentiated cells forms beneath the epithelium.
- Sustained mTOR Signaling: Maintains blastema formation and supports cellular differentiation.

hpa - Hours Post-Amputation
dpa - Days Post-Amputation

The timeline of blasthema formation

5. 28-56 dpa

- Tissue Remodeling: Newly formed tissues mature and integrate with existing structures.
- Limb Restoration: Fully functional limb and digits are restored.

4. 14-28 dpa

- Limb Bud Development: Blastema grows, forming a limb bud with distinct digit rays.
- Continued Differentiation: Cells continue to proliferate and differentiate under mTOR guidance.

A

B

Molecular level

REGENERATION CHAIN

- axmTOR detects amino acids
- axmTOR forms a stable dimer that binds RHEB, a protein necessary for mTORC1 assembly and activation.
- Activated mTORC1 increases protein synthesis by promoting the translation of pre-existing mRNAs. RPL19a and CIRBP are rapidly translated.

mTORC1

mTORC2

AssayGenie

Cytoskeleton dynamics, cell proliferation & survival

mTOR inhibition by INK-128

- disruption leading to impaired regeneration
- delayed wound closure
- arrested digit formation
- elevated ROS
- Arrested at Blastema Stage: At 28 days post-amputation (dpa), all INK128-treated animals remained at the blastema stage while control animals developed well-formed limb buds with distinct digit rays.
- Reinitiation of Regeneration: Despite initial delays, axolotls treated with INK128 were able to reinitiate regeneration and form digits between 42 and 56 dpa, likely due to the eventual reactivation of the mTOR pathway.

A

Not infinite

- Repeated removals resulting in miniaturized limbs with less innervation

- **Age related diagnosis**
- **Alzheimer's**
- **Parkinson's**
- **organ failure**
 - **(kidney, liver, heart and lungs)**
- **cancer**
- **osteoporosis and more**

- **Regenerative medicine**
“process of replacing, engineering or regenerating human or animal cells, tissues or organs to restore or establish normal function”

Thank you!
Questions?

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Amphibian-derived wound healing promoting peptides

Introduction

Acute wound healing phases:

- Hemostasis,
- Inflammation,
- Cellular Proliferation,
- Maturation (Remodeling).

- ❑ Amphibian-derived peptides significantly promoted wound healing
- ❑ Their working mechanisms involved various types of actions

AH90

- AH90 was identified from the skin of *Odorrana grahami*
- AH90 greatly induced generation of transforming growth factor β 1

Transforming Growth Factor $\beta 1$

It is crucial regulator of cellular homeostasis:

- regulation of cell growth and differentiation,
- apoptosis,
- immune suppression,
- extracellular matrix production and remodeling,
- epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT),
- angiogenesis.

Materials and Methods

- Human epidermal keratinocyte cell line, HaCaT cells were cultured
- Their migration was examined by performing the wound scratch assay
- After in vitro cell models researchers performed in vivo tests on mice

Results

Results

Discussion and Conclusion

- AH90 induced generation of TGF- β 1
- TGF- β 1 promoted wound regeneration through various mechanisms
- AH90 has small molecular weight which corresponds to low production cost, making it widely applicable in clinic

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Zebrafish Heart Regeneration

Insights of Nature

RISHU.G.SHAH (9th SEM TMA) SCIENCE CLUB

Introduction

- CHD leading cause of mortality worldwide
- 23.3 million people estimated to die annually by 2030 due to CHD
- Current therapies
- No finite “cure”

Differences in regenerative capacities

- Damaged tissue — 2 different pathways
 - Difference between species
 - Zebrafish — most important vertebrate model
 - Cellular turnover and different tissues
 - Human cardiomyocytes turnover from age 25 to 75 decreases from 1% to 0.45%
 - First evidence of adult vertebrate heart regeneration
-
-

Zebrafish heart regeneration discovery

- Tissue injury models to study heart regeneration
 - Possible explanations of high regenerative capacity in Zebrafish
 - Limitations
-
-

- Zebrafish fully regenerates heart in 2 months after 20% ventricular resection, demonstrated by Poss & Keating in 2002

Origin of regenerated cardiac tissue

- Myocardium contributions to heart regeneration

 - Non muscular contributions to heart regeneration
-
-

Mechanisms promoting cardiac regeneration in zebrafish

- Regenerative cycle 4 stages — initial inflammatory, regeneration of endocardium & epicardium, proliferation of cardiomyocytes, fibrotic scar degradation.

Role of ROS in cardiac regeneration

- ROS
 - O₂ concentrations
 - NOX, DUOX, H₂O₂
 - PTP's — Dusp6 & PTP1b
-
-

Conclusion & Future recommendations

- Stimulation of multi-tissue and organ regeneration is promising
 - A highly promising pharmaceutical approach
 - Many barriers still exist in translating use into the clinic
 - Fearful potential of inducing neoplastic transformation
 - One should not lose sight of the great potential
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Resources

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-
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Thankyou !

Any questions ?

Spider Silk Properties for Tissue Engineering

Presenter: Tatia Tsnobiladze
Professor: Saba Iordanishvili

Content

1. **General Information: Structure Organization**
2. **Mechanical Stress and Elasticity**
3. **Biocompatibility**
4. **Biodegradability**
5. **Cellular Interactions**
6. **Structural Versatility**

:General Information: Relevance

- ❑ offers new solutions for medical challenges**
- ❑ alternative to synthetic materials**
- ❑ potential in drug delivery systems and regenerative medicine**
- ❑ aligns with eco-friendly medical practices**

General Information : Structure

Natural polymeric fiber with high tensile strength and flexibility

- **Primary Structure:** Spidroins composed of Repetitive amino acid sequences (glycine and alanine)
- **Secondary Structure:** β -sheets for strength and α -helices for flexibility
- **Tertiary Structure:** nanocrystalline β -sheets and amorphous regions
- **Quaternary Structure:** Assembly of spidroins into fibers

Mechanical Stress and Elasticity

➤ Mechanical Strength

- High tensile Strength withstands substantial stress
- **Benefit:** engineered scaffolds support mechanical loads without failing (bone and ligament regeneration)

➤ Elasticity

- stretches up to five times its original length without breaking
- **Benefit:** allowing the scaffolds to accommodate movements without damage (skin and blood vessels)

Biocompatibility

- **Non-Toxic:** In vitro and in vivo studies show cell proliferation on spider silk without adverse effects
- **Minimal Inflammation:** In vitro implant provoked no significant immune response
- **Benefit:** promoting better integration of the silk-based scaffolds with surrounding tissues

Microbes

Mammalian cells

Scaffold designed including silk fibers and platelets

Biodegradability

- **Natural Degradation:** gradually breaks down through enzymatic action
- **Benefit:** ideal for resorbable scaffolds that provide support during the initial stages of tissue regeneration

Cellular Interactions

- ❑ Supports Cell Adhesion

- **Benefit:** ensures attachment, spreading and formation of new tissue on the scaffold

- ❑ Enhances Differentiation

- **Benefit:** provides a conducive environment for stem cells to develop into functional tissues (bone, cartilage, and nerve cells)

Adhesion and survival of human urothelial cells (HUCs) on natural spider silk fibers

Structural Versatility

- **Customizable Structures:** processed into various forms (fibers, films, hydrogels, sponges)
- **Benefit:** scaffolds with specific mechanical and biological properties tailored to the needs of the target tissue

SPIDER SILK

Nephila claviceps

Nephila edulis

Argiope aurantia

Araneus didematus

Host organism

Bacteria

Yeast cells

Eucariotic cells

Morphology

Foam

Fiber

Film

Hydrogel

Non-woven

Applications

- Skin
- Muscle
- Ligament
- Bone
- Cartilage
- Nerve
- Vessel
- Heart
- Breast
- Bladder

Recourses

- <https://www.mdpi.com/2313-7673/9/3/169#:~:text=The%20first%20clinical%20use%20of,tissues%20%5B17%2C18%5D.>
- https://www.researchgate.net/publication/357177514_Spider_Silk-Inspired_Artificial_Fibers
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Thank you for your Attention

Questions?

Bear metabolism in hibernation

Possible applications to humans.

Mariami Tsiklauri

Ekaterina Lunina

Effects of 6 months of bed rest	Human	Hibernating bears
Circulation	Heart failure Blood clots	No heart failure No blood clots
Muscle	Dramatic reduction in muscle mass	≈10–15% reduction in muscle mass
Bone	Severe disuse osteoporosis Hypercalcemia	No osteoporosis Normocalcemia
Metabolism	Carbohydrate, protein, and fat breakdown	Primarily fat breakdown
Skin	Bed sores	No bed sores

Bears are able to

Conserve muscles while sedentary and hibernating for 4 to 7 months every year

Go into insulin resistance specifically to use fat for energy

Reverse insulin resistance upon the end of hibernation

Avoid blood clots

Focus of this presentation:

Changes in:

Muscle

Fat

Liver

Blood

Comprehensive RNA-sequencing of muscle, liver and fat tissues during three periods.

Hibernation and non-hibernation.
Differentially expressed genes in adipose, liver, and muscle

Adipose tissue, muscle tissue

April

October

Hyperphagia: 984 differentially expressed genes.

Adipose tissue, muscle tissue

Hibernation:

- reduced expression HK1 and GCK
- LOC113264107 - non coding RNA gene highest connectivity.
- SHIP1 and SHIP2 upregulated-> reduce GLUT4 expression in fat and muscle -> induce insulin resistance.

April

October

Adipose tissue, muscle tissue

14 genes with differential expression associated with insulin resistance in common between bears and humans.

April

October

Liver tissue

INSR

GLUT2

Fructose-2,6 bisphosphatase 1

HK1 and GCK

Net effect: gluconeogenesis > glycolysis.

Liver's urea cycle down regulation.

Muscle preservation

Deep vein thrombosis

References

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The History and Role of CRISPR

Presented by Suliko Gogichashvili

Introduction

Discover of CRISPR

- CRISPR was first observed in 1987 in the bacterium *Escherichia coli* by **Dr. Yoshizumi Ishino** who noticed an unusual sequence of DNA containing repeating elements separated by unique spacers.
- **Emmanuelle Charpentier** and **Jennifer Doudna** received the Nobel Prize in Chemistry in **2020** for their development of CRISPR-Cas9, a revolutionary tool for precise genome editing.

Mechanism of CRISPR Function

CRISPR/Cas Mechanism

- The mechanism of CRISPR/Cas defence **involves three stages- spacer acquisition, expression (crRNA biogenesis) and interference.**
- The first stage, **adaptation**, leads to insertion of new spacers in the CRISPR locus.
- In the second stage, **expression**, the system gets ready for action by expressing the *cas* genes and transcribing the CRISPR into a long precursor CRISPR RNA (pre-crRNA). The pre-crRNA is subsequently processed into mature crRNA by Cas proteins and accessory factors.
- In the third and last stage, **interference**, target nucleic acid is recognized and destroyed by the combined action of crRNA and Cas proteins. i.e. **crRNA-Cas ribonucleoprotein** complex targets the invading nucleic acid for degradation.

Diversity of CRISPR-Cas Systems

- **Type I Systems:** These systems are defined by the presence of the Cas3 protein, which has both helicase and DNase activities, crucial for degrading the target DNA.
- **Type II Systems:** The most well-known CRISPR-Cas system, including the famous Cas9 protein, which has been extensively used in genetic engineering. Cas9 is responsible for cutting DNA at specific sites, guided by crRNA and a trans-activating crRNA (tracrRNA).
- **Type III Systems:** These systems target both DNA and RNA and are characterized by the presence of the Cas10 protein. They are unique in their ability to target and cleave both types of nucleic acids, providing a broader scope of defense.

CRISPR in Bacteria and Archaea

- CRISPR systems are found in approximately **84%** of **archaea** and **45%** of **bacteria**.
- The presence of CRISPR in both chromosomal and plasmid DNA of prokaryotes allows these organisms to maintain a chronological record of past infections, providing a robust and heritable form of immunity
- This feature is crucial for unicellular organisms that cannot rely on complex, multicellular immune responses.

CRISPR Beyond Immunity

- CRISPR systems have been found to play roles in **regulating gene expression** and **maintaining genome stability**.
- These discoveries highlight the versatility of CRISPR as a molecular tool, both in nature and in biotechnology.

Impact on Genetic Engineering

- The discovery of CRISPR-Cas systems, **particularly the Cas9** protein, has revolutionized the field of genetic engineering.
- **Patient Victoria Gray:** In 2019, Victoria Gray became the first patient in the United States to receive CRISPR treatment for **sickle cell anemia**.
- In 2019, a patient with **beta-thalassemia** was treated with CRISPR at the University Hospital in Germany.
- **HIV Elimination in Mice:** In 2019, scientists successfully used CRISPR to eliminate HIV from the genomes of mice,

Conclusion

- *The journey of CRISPR from its initial identification in *E. coli* to its extensive use in genetic engineering showcases both the brilliance of natural processes and the strength of scientific exploration.*

Thank you for listening